

MOTIVATING TECHNIQUES FOR LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

The main goal of this techniques is to show how pictures and videos can be put to use in English classes in a few ways and to answer the questions how and why this works and in what way exactly they help the learner remember the words and develop their all language skills.

Key words: pictures, videos, language, discussion, description, learning, goal

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At the lesson teachers can use the techniques such as “Picture prompt” and “Video demonstration” for teaching English adjectives as a vocabulary chunks. To be more specific, beside lessons where pictures and videos are in the main focus, they might be used just as a “stimulus for writing and discussion, as an illustration of something being read or talked about, as background to a topic and so on”. There are many reasons for using pictures and videos in language teaching. They motivate and draw learners’ attention, they provide a sense of the context of the language and give a specific reference of point or stimulus. Pictures and videos, being suitable for any context or group of learners independently on age or level, can be used in lots of various ways.

Picture Prompt gives students an image of film heroes, and teacher can ask them to describe it by using the adjectives, and justify their answers or ask students to write about it using terms from lecture, or to name the processes and concepts shown. Also works well as group activity. By watching video demonstrations of famous films with famous actors students can describe them by learned adjectives during the lesson.

Teacher can motivate students in learning English by using feature films, and assessing their comprehension on it by asking adjective descriptions. The results provided the students with current, meaningful and relevant content, and the combination of both an autonomous learning environment and collaborative, communicative, task-based on interaction. Videos and Pictures are one of the important ways of raising the motivation to learn the language. Teacher can use topic related pictures and videos for teaching adjective based on vocabulary and they made learners to activate all language skills while they begin to produce their comprehension on pictures and videos. Using of photos of famous actors with the intention helps to raise learners’ motivation.

In its turn teacher can use photos taken from internet sources and video materials as authentic and applied multimedia resources by developing slides of colorful stickers which serve really helpful to raise their motivation. As well as teachers use the handouts that serve much more in developing the students all four skills and use their gained knowledge for grammar comprehension of the new material.

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During microteaching each learner tries to participate actively while completing the tasks, it should be organized pair work and group works too for reading and speaking. Teacher need to use short and clear imperative sentences for instructing the learners.

The following expected results can be achieved during the lesson:

Be able to share their opinions and give a physical and personal description of someone they know using the appropriate adjectives introduced during the class.

Be able to use language involved with personal adjectives.

However, they are able to share their remembered things with the help of pictures and freely activate the learned vocabulary.

Using of topics related to pictures to develop all language skills motivates the learners to learn the language.

Using of videos plays an important role in the ESP instruction by providing students the proper environment to activate students' motivation and enhance their listening skill in their classrooms.

To assure effectiveness of the study, sufficient time is needed for teaching and learning listening skill. Providing of various videos: movies, video clips, TV shows, news, TV commercials; for studying whether using various kinds of videos (genre) affect listening ability. A variety of videos can motivate students learning English as a foreign language.

It is said that shooting own classes in the video in order to reflect on and study own teaching give plenty opportunities to create interesting and productive lessons. Moreover, teachers should try to use different modes of interactions. Each type of work-individual, pair and group- has its place in the language classroom as they can help effective language learning.

The main goal of this techniques is to show how pictures and videos can be put to use in English classes in a few ways and to answer the questions how and why this works and in what way exactly they help the learner remember the words and develop their all language skills.

These techniques are function as a guide to some, possibly not so experienced teachers, guiding them through vocabulary teaching and providing particular aid in the form of the lesson plan and activities included in it.

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